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A Comparative Study of the Productivity Index of Horizontal Well

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

This study looks into the comparison of the different productivity index model, in other to know that which will be suitable for high productivity and it also investigates the effect of reservoir and well parameters on the productivity index of horizontal well. It also analyses the effect of skin due to partial completion on productivity index using the three partial well completion configurations of Brons and Marting.

The results indicate that PI increases with increase well length for all the productivity index models, the Giger's model will produce a higher productivity than the other models for the same well length variations. It also shows PI increased with increase in well length and anisotropy value, and that horizontal wells are better suited for thin beds. The result of the effect of completion method on skin shows that wells that are perforated at equal interval along the wellbore experienced a little or no skin effect thereby enhancing productivity.

Keywords: Comparative study, Productivity index, Horizontal well models, Horizontal well.

INTRODUCTION

Horizontal wells are drilled basically for the reason of producing more oil or gas than a vertical well. When an engineer is in the process of deciding to drill a horizontal well or vertical well, one of the first considerations that is taken is the ratio of horizontal productivity to vertical productivity. Besides being a function of the reservoir and well properties, these ratios have the underlying assumption that the wellbore pressure is constant. These ratios can lead an engineer to believing that horizontal well will produce two or more times the production of a vertical well. Therefore, the productivity of a horizontal well depends on the length of the horizontal section embedded in the reservoir and the perforation percentage of the horizontal section¹.

In the presence of one phase flow, it is assumed that the production in a horizontal well is directly proportional to the pressure difference between the reservoir and the wellbore. The constant of proportional is the productivity index, 'j' defined as $q/\Delta p$, where 'q' is the flow rate and Δp is the pressure.

A lot of factors affect pressure in the reservoir and wellbore, thereby affecting the productivity index of the well. These factors include reservoir drainage area, pay zone thickness, anisotropy kv/kh, well length, fluid viscosity etc. Another factor that greatly affects pressure drawdown is the well completion method. In this case, we can have pressure loss due to perforation (ΔP_{perf}), pressure loss due to partial penetration (ΔP_p), pressure loss due to gravel pack environment (ΔP_{gp}) i.e. if gravel packing is done. During drilling, permeability can be damaged around the wellbore region and so pressure loss due to damage can also occur². Productivity index is a valuable methodology for predicting the future performance of wells.

Aims and Objectives

The objective of this work is to carry out a comparative study of the different horizontal well productivity index models, determine the effect of partial well completion and other reservoir/ well parameters on the productivity index of a well.

Scope of Study

This paper will involve how the different models of horizontal well productivity index affects the performance of a well, the types of horizontal well completion methods such as open hole, perforated lines and gravel packing. Also the reservoir/well parameters that affect the productivity index (PI) of a well.

METHODOLOGY

The different horizontal well productivity index equations was compared, the effect of well and Reservoir parameter, effect of completion methods, as well as well length and drainage area was calculated to determine how they affect the productivity index of horizontal wells.

Determination of Productivity Index Using Different Horizontal Well Models

Using the following Reservoir, Fluid and Well Data from Well A

Table 1: Reservoir, Fluid and Well Data

Reservoir Data	Fluid Data	Well Data
$K_h = 75\text{md}$ $K_v = 75\text{md}$ $H = 160\text{ft}$	$\mu_o = 0.62\text{cp}$ $B_o = 1.35\text{rb/STB}$	$L = 1000\text{ft}$ $r_w = 0.365\text{ft}$ $r_{eh} = 1053\text{ft}$ $A = 80\text{acres}$

Using Borisov's Model

$$J_h = \frac{q_h}{P_r - P_{wf}} = \frac{0.00708k_h h}{\mu_o B_o \left[\ln\left(\frac{4reh}{L}\right) + \frac{h}{L} \ln\left(\frac{h}{2\pi r_w}\right) \right]}$$

Inputting the various values into the equation, we have

$$J_h = \frac{0.00708 \times 75 \times 25}{(0.62 \times 1.35) \left[\ln\left(\frac{4 \times 1053}{1000} + \frac{160}{1000} \ln\left(\frac{160}{2\pi \times 0.365}\right) \right) \right]}$$

$$J_h = \frac{84.96}{(0.873) \left[\ln(4.212) + 0.16 \ln(69.77) \right]}$$

$$J_h = \frac{84.96}{(0.873) \left[1.438 + 0.679 \right]}$$

$$J_h = \frac{84.96}{1.774} = 47.95 \text{STB/day-psi}$$

Using Joshi's Model²

$$J_h = \frac{q_o}{P_r - P_{wf}} = \frac{0.00708\beta K_h h}{\mu_o B_o \left[\ln\left(\frac{a + \sqrt{a^2 - (L/2)^2}}{\frac{L}{2}}\right) + \left(\frac{\beta h}{L}\right) \ln\left(\frac{\left(\frac{\beta h}{L}\right)^2 + \beta^2 \delta^2}{\left(\frac{\beta h r_w}{2}\right)}\right) \right]}$$

Where:

$$a = \left(\frac{L}{2}\right) \left[0.5 + \sqrt{0.25 + \left(\frac{2reh}{L}\right)^4} \right]^{0.5}$$

$$\beta = \sqrt{K_h/K_v}$$

$$\delta = \frac{h}{2} - d$$

Inputting the various values into equation, we have

$$a = (1000/2)[0.5 + \sqrt{0.25 + (2 * 1053/1000)^4}]^{0.5}$$

$$a = 500[0.5 + 4.46]^{0.5}$$

$$a = 500[2.23] = 1115$$

$$\beta = \sqrt{\frac{75}{75}} = 1$$

$$\delta = \frac{160}{2} - 80 = 1$$

$$J_h = \frac{0.00708 \times 75 \times 160}{0.62 \times 1.35 \left[\ln \left(\frac{1115 + \sqrt{1115^2 - (1000/2)^2}}{1000} \right) + \left(\frac{160}{1000} \right) \ln \left(\frac{\left(\frac{160}{1000} \right)^2 + 1}{\left(\frac{160 \times 0.365}{2} \right)} \right) \right]}$$

$$J_h = \frac{84.96}{0.837[1.441 + 0.16(219.21)]}$$

$$J_h = \frac{84.96}{1.926}$$

$$J_h = 44.07 \text{ STB/day-psi}$$

Using Giger's Model³

$$J_h = \frac{q_o}{Pr - P_{wf}} = \frac{0.00708 K_h L}{\mu_o B_o \left[\left(\frac{L}{2} \right) \ln \left(\frac{1 + \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{L}{2reh} \right)^2}}{\frac{L}{2reh}} \right) + \ln \left(\frac{h}{(2\pi rw)} \right) \right]}$$

$$J_h = \frac{0.00708 \times 75 \times 1000}{0.837 \left[\left(\frac{1000}{2} \right) \ln \left(\frac{1 + \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{1000}{2} \times 1053 \right)^2}}{1000} \right) + \ln \left(\frac{160}{(2\pi \times 0.365)} \right) \right]}$$

$$J_h = \frac{531}{0.837 \left[6.25 \ln \left(\frac{1.8803}{0.475} \right) + \ln \left(\frac{160}{(2.293)} \right) \right]}$$

$$J_h = \frac{531}{0.837[6.25 \ln(3.959) + \ln(69.78)]}$$

$$J_h = \frac{531}{0.837[8.6 + 4.25]}$$

$$J_h = \frac{531}{10.70}$$

$$J_h = 49.35 \text{ STB/day-psi}$$

Using Renard and Dupuy Model⁸

$$J_h = \frac{q_o}{Pr - P_{wf}} = \frac{0.00708 K_h h}{\mu_o B_o \left[\cosh^{-1} \left(\frac{2a}{L} \right) + \left(\frac{h}{L} \right) \ln \left(\frac{h}{(2\pi rw)} \right) \right]}$$

Where:

$$a = \left(\frac{L}{2} \right) \left[0.5 + \sqrt{0.25 + \left(\frac{2reh}{L} \right)^4} \right]^{0.5}$$

$$a = \left(\frac{1000}{2}\right) \left[0.5 + \sqrt{0.25 + \left(\frac{2 \times 1053}{1000}\right)^4}\right]^{0.5}$$

$$a = 1115$$

Inputting values into equation, we have

$$J_h = \frac{0.00708 \times 75 \times 160}{0.62 \times 1.35 \left[\cosh^{-1} \left(\frac{2 \times 1115}{1000} \right) + \left(\frac{160}{1000} \right) \ln \left(\frac{160}{(2\pi \times 0.365)} \right) \right]}$$

$$J_h = \frac{84.96}{0.837 [\cosh^{-1}(2.23) + (0.16) \ln(69.77)]}$$

$$J_h = \frac{84.96}{0.837(1.441 + 0.679)}$$

$$J_h = \frac{84.96}{1.774}$$

$$J_h = 47.89 \text{ STB/day-psi}$$

Effect of Length and Anisotropy on Productivity Index

The following reservoir and well data are available for well A.

$$k_h = 75 \text{ md}$$

$$h = 25 \text{ ft}$$

$$\mu_o = 0.62 \text{ cp}$$

$$B_o = 1.34 \text{ rb/stb}$$

$$r_w = 0.365 \text{ ft}$$

$$K_v/K_h = 0.1, 0.5, 1.0$$

Well length: 100, 500, 900, 1300 and 1700

Horizontal well productivity index using well Length can be calculated using the following Equation.

$$J_h = (0.00708 K_h h) / (\mu_o B_o) \ln \left[\left(\frac{a + \sqrt{a^2 - (L/2)^2}}{L/2} \right) + \left(\frac{\beta h}{L} \right) \ln \left(\frac{\beta h}{2r_w} \right) \right] \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$\beta = \sqrt{K_h/K_v}$$

For $K_v/K_h = 0.1$

$$\beta = \sqrt{10} = 3.16$$

$$L = 100 \text{ ft}$$

$$a = \left(\frac{L}{2}\right) \left[0.5 + \sqrt{0.25 + \left(\frac{2r_e h}{L}\right)^4}\right]^{0.5}$$

$$a = 100/2 \left[0.5 + \sqrt{0.25 + (2 * 1053/100)^4}\right]^{0.5}$$

$$a = 1054$$

$$\left(\frac{\beta h}{L}\right) \ln \left(\frac{\beta h}{2r_w}\right)$$

$$= (3.16 \times 25/100) \ln [(3.26 \times 25)/(2 \times 0.365)]$$

$$= 3.68$$

$$L = 100 \text{ ft}$$

$$a = \left(\frac{L}{2}\right) \left[0.5 + \sqrt{0.25 + \left(\frac{2r_e h}{L}\right)^4}\right]^{0.5}$$

$$a = 100/2 \left[0.5 + \sqrt{0.25 + (2 * 1053/100)^4}\right]^{0.5}$$

$$a = 1054$$

$$\left(\frac{\beta h}{L}\right) \ln \left(\frac{\beta h}{2r_w}\right)$$

$$= (3.16 \times 25/100) \ln (3.16/2 \times 0.365)$$

$$= 3.68$$

$$J_h = \frac{0.00708 \times 75 \times 25}{(0.62 \times 1.34) \ln \left[\frac{1054 + \sqrt{1054^2 - \left(\frac{100}{2}\right)^2}}{\frac{100}{2}} \right] + 3.68}$$

$$J_h = \frac{15.978}{3.74 + 3.68} = 2.15 \text{ STB/day/psi}$$

Effect of Well Thickness on Productivity Index

Using the same parameters given for well A

Different well thickness: 25ft, 50ft, and 50ft.

Well length = 100ft, 500ft, 900ft, 1300ft and 1700ft.

Productivity index (PI) is calculated for each reservoir and various well lengths by using the equation below:

$$J_h = (0.00708 K_h h) / (\mu_o B_o) \ln \left[\frac{a + \sqrt{a^2 - (L/2)^2}}{L/2} \right] + \left(\frac{L}{2}\right) \ln \left(\frac{h}{2r_w}\right) \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

L = 100ft

$$a = \left(\frac{L}{2}\right) \left[0.5 + \sqrt{0.25 + \left(\frac{2reh}{L}\right)^4} \right]^{0.5}$$

$$a = 100/2 \left[0.5 + \sqrt{0.25 + (2 * 1053/100)^4} \right]^{0.5}$$

a = 1054

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\frac{L}{2}\right) \ln(h/2r_w) \\ &= (100/2) \ln(25/2 \times 0.365) \\ &= 0.883 \end{aligned}$$

Substituting into formula, we have

$$J_h = \frac{0.00708 \times 75 \times 25}{(0.62 \times 1.34) \ln \left[\frac{1054 + \sqrt{1054^2 - \left(\frac{100}{2}\right)^2}}{\frac{100}{2}} \right] + 0.883}$$

$$J_h = \frac{15.978}{3.74 + 0.883} = 3.36 \text{ STB/day-psi}$$

The same procedure is used to calculate for h = 500ft, 900ft, 1300ft and 1700ft.

Effect of Drainage Area on Productivity Index

Using well A parameter,

Drainage area = 20ft, 40ft, 60ft, and 80ft.

Drainage radius, $r_e = \sqrt{A \times 43,560/\pi}$ (for a circular drainage area) (3)

Equation 1 and 3 is used to calculate PI for different values of Kv/Kh = 0.1, 0.5, 1.0 and for different drainage area.

Example 3.3

For drainage area = 20

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Drainage radius} &= \sqrt{(20 \times 43,560)/\pi} \\ &= 527\text{ft} \end{aligned}$$

L = 500ft

Kv/ Kh = 0.1

$$a = (500/2) \left[0.5 + \sqrt{0.25 + (2 * 527/500)^4} \right]^{0.5}$$

a = 557ft

$\beta = \sqrt{10} = 3.16$

Using this equation

$$J_h = (0.00708K_h h)/(\mu_o B_o) \ln \left[\frac{a + \sqrt{a^2 - (L/2)^2}}{\frac{L}{2}} \right] + \left(\frac{\beta h}{L} \right) \ln \left(\frac{\beta h}{2r_w} \right)$$

Inputting values into equation, we have

$$J_h = \frac{0.00708 \times 75 \times 25}{(0.62 \times 1.34) \ln \left[\frac{557 + \sqrt{557^2 - \left(\frac{500}{2}\right)^2}}{\frac{500}{2}} \right] + (3.16 \times \frac{25}{500}) \ln \left[\frac{3.16 \times 25}{2 \times 0.365} \right]}$$

$$J_h = \frac{15.978}{1.4396 + 0.7401}$$

$$J_h = 7.3304 \text{ STB/day-psi}$$

The same procedure is used to calculate for drainage area = 40ft, 60ft and 80ft.

Effect of Well Completion on Productivity Index

When a well undergoes completion, three types of skin occurs

- (1) Skin due to perforation, S_p
- (2) Skin due to penetration, S_a
- (3) Skin due to crush zone permeability, S_c

Considering the case of skin due to penetration, some wells are fully penetrated along the interval of interest. In this case, S_a tend to zero (0); other wells are partially penetrated along the interval of interest, this results in pseudo skin due to partial completion. This kind of completion restricts fluid entry into the wellbore⁷.

The analyses on effect of completion on productivity will only be considered for a partially completed well.

Calculation of Pseudoskin Factor Due to Partial Penetration

Using Brons and Marting method¹⁴, which consider three (3) types of partial well completion configuration:

- (a) Well producing from the top (or bottom) of the formation.
- (b) Well only producing from the central section.
- (c) Well with N intervals open to production (five (5) open intervals).

For three (3) wells producing from the same reservoir and are completed using either of the configurations given above, pseudo skin due to partial penetration can be calculated from which we will obtain the productivity index for each well. Pseudo skin factor is calculated using the equation,

$$S_p = (1/b' - 1)[\ln(h_D) - G(b')]$$

Where b' has already been defined as:

$b' = hp/h$, (penetration ratio)

$$h_D = h/r_w \sqrt{\frac{K_h}{K_v}} \text{ (dimensionless pay zone thickness)}$$

hp = perforated interval, ft.

h = total pay zone thickness, ft.

For horizontal well $h = L$ i.e. lateral length which might be greater than h i.e. $L > h$.

$$G(b') = 2.948 - 7.363b' + 11.45(b')^2 - 4.675(b')^3$$

Given the following well/reservoir parameters

$$\begin{aligned} hp &= 20\text{ft} \\ h &= 100\text{ft} \\ K_v/K_h &= 0.5 \\ r_w &= 0.365\text{ft} \end{aligned}$$

Calculating for S_p as described for three cases in Brons and Martings method gives;
Solution:

$$b' = hp/h = 20/200 = 0.2$$

Case A:

$$h_D = h/r_w \sqrt{\frac{K_h}{K_v}}$$

$$h_D = \frac{100}{0.365} \sqrt{2} = 387.4$$

$$\begin{aligned} G(b') &= 2.948 - 7.363(0.2) + 11.45(0.2)^2 - 4.675(0.2)^3 \\ &= 2.948 - 1.4726 + 0.458 - 0.0374 \\ &= 1.896 \end{aligned}$$

$$S_p = \left(\frac{1}{0.2} - 1\right) [\ln(387.4) - 1.896] = 16.254$$

Case B:

$$h_D = h/2r_w \sqrt{\frac{K_h}{K_v}}$$

$$= \frac{100}{2 \times 0.365} \sqrt{2} = 193.7$$

$$S_p = \left(\frac{1}{0.2} - 1\right) [\ln(193.7) - 1.896] = 13.484$$

Case C:

$$h_D = h/2Nr_w \sqrt{\frac{K_h}{K_v}}$$

$$= \frac{100}{2 \times 5 \times 0.365} \sqrt{2} = 38.7$$

$$S_p = \left(\frac{1}{0.2} - 1\right) [\ln(38.7) - 1.896] = 6.977$$

From the calculation, it is seen that skin (S_p) is less in case 3 than the first 2 cases. The productivity index as a result of skin is calculated using the equation⁴;

$$J_h = (0.00708K_h h) / (\mu_o B_o) \ln \left[\frac{\alpha + \sqrt{\alpha^2 - \left(\frac{L}{2}\right)^2}}{\frac{L}{2}} \right] + \left(\frac{L}{2}\right) \ln \left(\frac{h}{2r_w}\right) + S_a$$

Given the parameters for well A (CASE A)

$$J_h = \frac{0.00708 \times 75 \times 25}{(0.62 \times 1.34) \ln \left[\frac{1054 + \sqrt{1054^2 - \left(\frac{100}{2}\right)^2}}{\frac{100}{2}} \right] + 3.68 + 16.252}$$

$$J_h = \frac{15.978}{3.74 + 3.68 + 16.252} = 0.675 \text{ STB/day/psi}$$

There is a reduction in the productivity index of the well; this can be accounted for by pseudo skin due to partial penetration.

Using parameters, Wells A, S_a and PI will be calculated for in the three (3) Cases with different penetration ratio; 0.2, 0.4, 0.6 and 0.8

RESULT AND ANALYSIS

This shows the results obtained from different well length for the different models.

Table2: Results of horizontal well models on productivity index variation with well length

Jh (STB/day-psi)				
MODELS	BORISOV'S	JOSHI'S	GIGER'S	RENARD AND DUPUY
WELL LENGTH				
1000	47.65	44.07	49.35	47.89
1300	59.62	55.06	63.97	59.62
1500	68.30	62.84	76.73	67.97
1700	77.73	71.16	94.23	74.92
2000	93.47	84.96	152.80	91.55

Fig.1: A plot of the different horizontal well productivity index models versus well length variation

Fig.1 and Table 2 shows us that the longer the well length, the higher the productivity index. Horizontal well productivity can be seen to be affected by well length because a shorter well length will produce a minimum productivity index compared to a longer well length. From table 2, it is seen that the Giger's productivity index model will produce a higher productivity for each well length when compared to the other models used.

Table 3: Data showing variation of PI with Well length and anisotropy

Jh (STB/day-psi)			
Thickness, h=25ft			
Length	Kv/Kh=0.1	Kv/Kh=0.5	Kv/Kh=1
100	2.15	3.13	3.46
500	5.58	6.66	6.92
900	8.19	9.45	9.73
1300	10.94	12.39	12.68
1700	14.02	15.98	16.47

FIG.2: A PLOT OF PI VARIATION WITH WELL LENGTH AND ANISOTROPY

Fig.2 shows that the productivity index (PI) will increase with increasing lateral length. Thus, longer horizontal well length enhances or increases productivity. This is explained by the fact that a large portion of the reservoir has been contacted and the pressure drop along the wellbore is reduced, enhancing productivity. In the case of anisotropy, it shows that horizontal wells are more suitable for reservoirs with high vertical permeability, K_v as thus will increase horizontal well productivity index.

Table4: Effect of well thickness on Productivity index (PI) variation with well thickness

Thickness Length (ft)	Jh (STB/day-psi)		
	25ft	50ft	100ft
100	3.46	5.48	7.54
500	6.93	12.52	20.77
900	9.77	18.25	30.93
1300	12.81	23.76	41.37
1700	16.42	30.64	53.30

Fig.3: A PLOT OF PI VARIATION WITH WELL THICKNESS

Fig 3 shows that the incremental gain in productivity is much higher in a thick reservoir than in a thin reservoir but when productivity ratio J_h/J_v is calculated for reservoir thickness, we will discover that a thin reservoir produces more than a thick reservoir. This is as a result of a wellbore exposure to the formation. Therefore, we can say that horizontal wells are more productive in thin reservoir than in thick ones. In a thick reservoir, a horizontal well behaves like a vertical well because of the small exposure of the wellbore to the formation.

Table 5: Effect area on productivity index (PI) variation of drainage with drainage area and anisotropy

Jh (STB/day-psi)			
Drainage area area	Kv/Kh=0.1	Kv/Kh=0.5	Kv/Kh=1
20	7.33	9.32	9.89
40	6.33	7.76	8.14
60	5.86	7.07	7.38
80	5.53	6.64	6.92

FIG.4: A PLOT OF PI VARIATION DRAINAGE AREA AND ANISOTROPY

Fig. 4 shows that horizontal well productivity index will increase slightly decreasing drainage area.

Completion Effects on Productivity Index (Partially Completed Wells)

In this case, only partially well completion was considered and the effect of partially penetration which results in skin productivity index.

Table 6: Variation of productivity index with penetration ratio and pseudo skin for partially completed well (Brons and Marting correlation)

b'	CASE A SP	Jh (STB/day-psi) PI
0.2	16.254	0.675
0.4	6.635	1.137
0.6	2.878	1.552
0.8	0.992	1.899
CASE B		
0.2	13.848	0.7513
0.4	5.5956	1.2276
0.6	2.4157	1.6245
0.8	0.8185	1.9394
CASE C		
0.2	6.977	1.1098
0.4	3.1803	1.5073
0.6	1.3423	1.8235
0.8	0.4160	2.0391

Fig.5: A plot of PI variation with penetration ratio for three different well completion configurations (case A, B, C)

Fig.6: A plot of PI variation with pseudo-skin for three different well completion configurations (case A, B, C)??

Effect of Pseudo-Skin Due To Partial Penetration on Productivity Index

Generally, the larger the skin, the lower the productivity index (PI) of a well. This effect is however more pronounced for the vertical well. This is due to the multiplier h/L on the horizontal well skin. h is the pay zone thickness and L is the lateral length of the horizontal well. As L increases, the effect of skin on horizontal well productivity index reduces appreciably as shown in fig 6 (effect of pseudo-skin on PI ratio).

Effect of Penetration Ratio on Productivity Index

Fig 5 shows that productivity index increases with increasing penetration ratio. The analysis done for the three (3) well configuration shows that the case C i.e, the well with N interval opens to production, and is the best configuration for any partial well completion. The no opened interval on the liner allows for less pressure drop and allows for easy fluid entry into the wellbore. In doing so, the problems associated with skin will be reduced. In some cases, there are cases of no skin, hence no damage around the wellbore.

CONCLUSION

In my study, a comparative study of horizontal well productivity index was carried out and the factors affecting productivity in horizontal wells were considered and the following were observed

1. The factors which affect pressure drop between reservoir and the wellbore such as well length, permeability, reservoir thickness, drainage area, fluid viscosity and perforation percentage are also factors affecting productivity index in horizontal wells.
2. Productivity in horizontal wells does not only depend on the well length, but also on the type of completion used and the efficiency of the completion of work done.
3. Productivity index is affected by skin, those caused by completion include;
 - (a) Pseudo skin due to perforation
 - (b) Pseudo skin due to partial penetration
 - (c) Skin factor due to reduced crushed – zone permeability
 - (d) Rate – dependent skin factor due to near wellbore turbulence.
4. The higher the skin the lower the productivity index of a well and vice versa.

5. For the three partial well completion configuration method as proposed by Brons and Marting, the third configuration i.e. wells with N intervals open to production is the most acceptable completion method.

Nomenclature

a = Half major axis of drainage ellipse, ft
Bo = Oil formation volume factor, rb/stb
C = Elgaghad et al. parameter
CH = Babu and Odeh shape factor
h = Formation thickness
Jh = Horizontal well productivity index, STB/day-psi
K = Permeability, md
Kh = Horizontal permeability, md
Kv = Vertical permeability, md
L = Horizontal well length, ft
hp = perforated interval, ft
Pr = Average reservoir pressure, psia
Pwf = Flowing wellbore pressure, psi
Qo = Oil flow rate, STB/day
rc = Radius of compacted zone, ft
reh = Horizontal well drainage radius, ft
rp = radius of compacted tunnel, ft
rw = Effective wellbore radius, ft
S = Skin factor
St = Total skin factor
Sm = Mechanical skin factor
Sp = Pseudo skin factor caused by partial
b' = Penetration ratio
 β = Anisotropy (Kh/Kv), dimensionless
Sr = Babu and Odeh
Lp = Penetration tunnel length
 ΔP = Pressure drop between the reservoir and wellbore, psi
 δ = Eccentricity factor
X = Renard and Dupuy area
 μ_o = Oil viscosity, cp

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